

1 Expression of E7 protein of HPV16 in C33A cells.

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7 Understanding viral protein function is difficult without cellular context that captures most closely
8 endogenous expression of the target and its network binding partners. We measured here total
9 transcription by RNA-sequencing in cultured C33A cervical epithelial cells following ectopic expression of
10 the E7 protein of HPV16 to describe E7 network interacts and cellular properties. Chief among changes in
11 cellular transcription was induction of histone H1-0. Pioneer factor assembly was affected with silencing of
12 *Hes1* and *Hey1*. Non-coding RNA expression changes observed included *Neat1* induction. E7 appeared
13 to support transformation through induction of *Msh5* and *Mus81*. E7-expressing cells underwent changes
14 in cell cycle including loss of *Cdk8* and *Cdc5l* expression with induction of a molecule known as *Cnppd1*.

15 Citations

16 1. Ciccolini, F., Di Pasquale, G., Carlotti, F., Crawford, L. and Tommasino, M., 1994. Functional
17 studies of E7 proteins from different HPV types. *Oncogene*, 9(9), pp.2633-2638.

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